

STRATEGIES TO SUPPORT WOMEN'S BUSINESSES IN THE INNOVATION SECTOR

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Abstract: The article states that one of the most important tasks in Uzbekistan is to support women's entrepreneurship and create conditions for them to earn a decent income.

Keywords: innovative economy, women's entrepreneurship, production, innovation, employment.

The development of entrepreneurship among women is one of the important ongoing processes on a global scale. Today, women make up a significant part of the working-age and economically active population of our country.

In accordance with the current changes in the world and the expansion of globalization processes, the problem of determining the place of women in small business and private entrepreneurship and the problems that need to be solved in this regard are still waiting for their solution. It is known that in Uzbekistan, suitable conditions have been created for improving the status and role of women, ensuring their rights and interests, increasing their socio-political and economic activity, and generally expanding their participation in the modernization of all aspects of life. The issues of equality between women and men and non-discrimination against women are stipulated in the Constitution. In particular, according to Article 37 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as Article 6 of the Labor Code, discrimination against women in labor relations is prohibited. If we analyze the economic activity of the world population based on gender approaches, it should be noted that women's employment is increasing [1]. In particular, the share of women in the economic activity of the population of Uzbekistan is much higher than in other countries. In particular, the share of our women employed in the economy has reached 60 percent, and the followers of our mothers, who are recognized for their high spirituality and enlightenment, exemplary manners and upbringing, today make invaluable contributions to state and social construction, production, science,

culture, medicine, education and even the military. The main factor in further improving the status of women in our country, increasing their socio-political activity, and ensuring their active participation in the reforms carried out in our country is the fact that thousands of our women are opening production enterprises in various areas of entrepreneurship, creating new jobs for women. Today, our opinion is confirmed by the establishment of the Coordinating Council for the Development of Women's Entrepreneurship in order to develop a comprehensive approach to the development of women's entrepreneurship, develop and implement programs to support women-led enterprises, provide them with access to information, markets, education and financial resources, and actively promote business activities among women.

They have provided practical assistance to about 28 thousand women in entrepreneurship, crafts, vocational retraining, and employment, and 21 thousand 500 young girls have been trained in short-term vocational courses [2]. In addition, it is planned to strengthen the concept of "Women's Entrepreneurship" in legislation, conduct a baseline study on the analysis of the investment climate in Uzbekistan, taking into account the gender approaches of the EBRD program, and develop a National Program for the Development of Women's Entrepreneurship.

Another important aspect is that the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, within the framework of the "Entrepreneur" program, allocates 10 million US dollars in loans. It is also important that the funds are directed to support small and medium-sized enterprises led by women in Uzbekistan. The number of women entrepreneurs has increased by almost 45 thousand in one year, and thousands of new jobs have been created by them. In recent years, within the framework of social programs "Every Family is an Entrepreneur", "Our Youth Future" and other programs aimed at attracting a wide range of the population to entrepreneurship and expanding their sources of income, a total of more than 13 trillion soums of preferential loans have been allocated, reaching more than 600 thousand families. Thus, today, more than 17 million of the population of Uzbekistan are women. To support their business projects and address their problems, a new system of training women in entrepreneurship, developing model business plans and providing them with practical assistance has been introduced. For this, more than 1 trillion soums have been allocated from the budget. It should also be noted that there are a number of international standards that determine the environment for women's entrepreneurship in a particular country, and its level of development is determined by an

international document that determines the rating of countries called the "Global Women's Entrepreneurship Index"[3]. The "Global Women's Entrepreneurship Index" measures the prospects for the development of women's entrepreneurship around the world. The quality of women's entrepreneurship development is determined by 3 main factors: the business environment, the entrepreneurial ecosystem and the desire of women to engage in entrepreneurship. A number of factors are taken into account when preparing this document. These include factors such as women's access to the education system and resources created in the business sector, the infrastructure of services provided by state bodies and commercial banks, and the collection and provision of statistical data on the development of women's entrepreneurship.

We consider it appropriate to implement the following measures to develop entrepreneurship, in particular women's entrepreneurship:

- issues of women's employment, gender equality and women's rights, socio-economic, legal and moral support for women;
- increasing gender equality and women's economic opportunities; investing more in increasing their economic opportunities;
- institutionally improving and developing the microcredit system aimed at supporting entrepreneurship;
- improving the legal framework for the development of women's economic opportunities and entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan and creating strong legal guarantees;
- attention to the development of women's economic opportunities and entrepreneurship, improving legislation in this regard and creating strong legal guarantees;
- exchange of experience with international organizations in expanding women's economic opportunities and developing women's entrepreneurship;
- improving international standards for women's entrepreneurship and national legislation in this regard;
- conducting a comparative analysis of the state of women's entrepreneurship among developed countries using global rating indicators.

In conclusion, it can be said that Uzbekistan's participation in the global rating will serve to identify measures to further improve the environment for women's entrepreneurship, as well as to achieve a positive approach from the international community.

References:

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